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SALMONELLOSIS IN POULTRY AND ITS SENSITIVITY TO ANTIBACTERIAL PREPARATIONS

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Abstract. This article provides information on the pathological changes caused by salmonellosis in poultry and the sensitivity of the disease to antibacterial preparations.

Keywords: *Salmonella*, *S. enterica*, antibiotic sensitivity, gram-negative, poultry farming, infection, infected farms.

Relevance of the topic: Poultry farming is one of the important and rapidly developing sectors of the economy in many countries. Poultry production makes it possible to obtain low-cost eggs and dietary meat. The task of increasing the competitiveness of the poultry industry in our country in domestic and foreign markets requires not only improving the economic efficiency of production but also ensuring ecological safety and obtaining high-quality products. The widespread use of antibiotics in livestock farming, particularly in poultry production, for the treatment of infectious diseases and as growth stimulants has led to the emergence of resistant microflora populations. (1; 2;)

Poultry farms around the world suffer significant economic losses due to mortality caused by salmonellosis in poultry, decreased productivity, and expenses related to disease prevention, treatment, and implementation of control measures. Eggs and poultry meat products contaminated with *Salmonella* are considered the main sources of foodborne toxicoinfections in humans. According to medical statistics, toxicoinfections of *Salmonella* etiology occur in almost all countries worldwide, and over the last twenty years, the increase in such infections among humans has primarily been associated with the spread of salmonellosis in domestic animals and poultry. Therefore, the diagnosis of salmonellosis in poultry and the development of effective control measures remain among the urgent tasks of modern veterinary science.

Salmonellosis is an infectious disease affecting most domestic and wild birds, as well as animals and humans. It is caused by bacteria belonging to the genus *Salmonella*. In young birds, the disease usually has an acute course characterized by lesions of the gastrointestinal and respiratory systems, septicemia, and high mortality among chicks. In adult birds, salmonellosis is mainly associated with lesions of the egg-producing organs and is often characterized by a chronic course without obvious clinical signs but with a high carrier state of *Salmonella* (3; 4; 5;).

In dead chicken embryos, the fluid within the yolk sac appears bluish-green in color, and necrotic foci are observed in the liver. The gallbladder is usually enlarged and filled with viscous bile. The rectum is dilated due to urinary salts or gas accumulation, and a large amount of urinary salts is also present in the allantois (6; 7; 8;).

In chicken embryos infected with *S. enteritidis* and in chicks up to two weeks of age, lung lesions are observed more frequently, whereas enteritis is commonly found in 30-day-old

chicks. In addition, the gallbladder is filled with dark light-brown (light yellow) bile mixed with fibrin and mucus (8; 9; 10;).

In chicks affected by salmonellosis, serous exudates mixed with fibrin particles are observed in the thoracic cavity. The lungs contain dense grayish-red lesions. Enlargement of the right ventricle results in a slight increase in heart size. Many authors have reported myocardial relaxation and congestion of the coronary vessels with blood (11;).

In 30.7% of broiler chicks, lesions of the leg joints, accumulation of fibrinous fluid, and inflammatory changes have been reported (12;).

Pathoanatomical changes in the lungs during avian salmonellosis are characterized by focal catarrhal pneumonia. Dystrophic changes with foci of coagulative necrosis have also been identified in the myocardium of dead birds (13; 14;).

A sharp decrease in egg production, damage to the digestive and reproductive systems, liver lesions (necrotic and dystrophic changes) and enteritis were recorded in 100% of diseased chickens. Oophoritis and ovariosalpingitis were observed in 90% of cases, while splenomegaly (enlargement of the spleen) was reported in 80% of the affected birds (15;).

Determining the antibiotic susceptibility of isolated strains is of great practical importance in the treatment and prevention of salmonellosis in chicks. The selection of antibiotics with high efficacy against *Salmonella* contributes to the effective implementation of preventive and therapeutic measures. In our study, the disk diffusion method was used to determine the susceptibility of the pathogen to antibiotics. The following antimicrobial preparations were tested: ENROFLOX 10% oral, ALBENDAZOLE 2.5%, Amoxicillin 150, Ivermek, and Oxytetracycline 50%.

The obtained results and their evaluation are presented in the following table (Table 1).

Table 1. Results of Determining the Antibiotic Sensitivity of Salmonellosis Pathogens in Poultry

No	Preparation name	Diameter of growth inhibition zone (mm)	Evaluation
1	ENROFLOX 10% oral	21	Sensitive
2	ALBENDAZOLE 2.5%	17	Sensitive
3	Amoxicillin 150	11	Low sensitivity
4	Ivermek	6	Very low sensitivity
5	Oxytetracycline 50%	25	Sensitive

In the experiments, ENROFLOX 10% oral, ALBENDAZOLE 2.5%, and Oxytetracycline 50% were found to inhibit bacterial growth within zones of 21 mm, 17 mm, and 25 mm, respectively. In addition, the *Salmonella* strains isolated from poultry showed low sensitivity to Amoxicillin 150 (11 mm), whereas Ivermek exhibited the lowest sensitivity level (6 mm).

Analysis of our in vitro studies demonstrated that three antibacterial preparations, namely ENROFLOX 10% oral, ALBENDAZOLE 2.5%, and Oxytetracycline 50%, are appropriate candidates for testing against avian salmonellosis. The observed susceptibility of the studied *Salmonella* bacteria to these preparations indicates that the *Salmonella* strains circulating in the investigated farms had not developed resistance to the above-mentioned agents. Regardless of the disease etiology, these preparations may be successfully applied in the treatment of salmonellosis.

Studies aimed at determining the effectiveness of antibacterial preparations used in poultry treatment involved the application of those agents that demonstrated high sensitivity to the investigated strain under laboratory in vitro conditions in experimental in vivo salmonellosis models. The following results were obtained.

The survival of poultry, recovery of health status, growth performance, restoration of live body weight, normalization of feed intake, and recovery time were considered indicators of successful treatment and recovery from the disease.

Conclusion: The findings of scientists and the results of our investigation on the sensitivity to antibacterial preparations demonstrated that infectious and contagious diseases occurring in poultry not only adversely affect bird health but also significantly reduce the economic efficiency of poultry farms. In particular, decreased productivity, impaired feed digestion, and weakened immunity remain among the most pressing problems in the poultry industry.

The study of antibacterial susceptibility showed that **ENROFLOX 10% oral, ALBENDAZOLE 2.5%, and Oxytetracycline 50%** exhibited high effectiveness against the isolated *Salmonella* strains, whereas **Amoxicillin 150** showed low sensitivity and **Ivermек** demonstrated the lowest sensitivity. The obtained results indicate that the *Salmonella* strains circulating in the studied poultry farms have not developed resistance to the above-mentioned highly effective preparations. Therefore, these antibacterial agents may be recommended for further *in vivo* studies and practical application in the treatment and prevention of poultry salmonellosis. Early diagnosis, appropriate selection of antibacterial preparations, and effective preventive measures play an important role in reducing the spread of the disease and improving the productivity and economic performance of poultry farming.

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